

Survival of *C. longipennis* using the mass rearing technique. IIRI insectary, 1986.

Stage	Insects reared (no.)	Surviving individuals (no.)	survival (%)
Egg to 1st instar	326	307	96
1st instar to adult	40	34	85

Third instars were transferred to 20.0-cm test tubes (2.5 cm in diameter) to complete nymphal development. Newly emerged adult males and females were confined in 30- × 22- × 52.5-cm rectangular mylar cages with separate petri dishes containing 2 g of corn borer diet and moist cotton on the bottom. The moist cotton provided water and served as a suitable substrate for oviposition.

C. longipennis completed its life cycle from egg to adult in 142 to 182 d, with 80% survival (see table). The corn borer diet was suitable for rearing the insect. □

Rearing field-collected grasshoppers in the laboratory.

Effect of insecticides on rice leaf folder (LF) eggs

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We studied nine insecticides to determine their ovicidal efficacy on eggs of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) in the insectary. The experiment was in a completely randomized design with three replications, with each replication consisting of 20 eggs.

Male and female LF moths obtained from mass culture were introduced in tumbler pots containing 25-d-old rice seedlings. The tumbler pots were covered with glass chimneys 22 cm high and 7.5 cm in diameter. Oviposition was observed daily. Seedlings containing eggs were separated and planted in tumbler pots.

Insecticidal treatments were given with a hand atomizer; control pots received water spray. Hatching of larvae was recorded for each treatment.

Phosphamidon, quinalphos, and monocrotophos treatments had 100% egg mortality; fenthion followed with 96% mortality (see table). Endosulfan exhibited the least ovicidal action. □

Ovicidal action of insecticides on rice LF eggs. Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Concn. (%)	Mortality ^a (%)
Monocrotophos 36 WSC	0.05	100 a
Quinalphos 25 EC	0.05	100 a
Phosphamidon 85 WSC	0.045	100 a
Fenthion 100 EC	0.01	96 a
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	0.04	54 b
Malathion 50 EC	0.1	46 b
Dichlorvos 100 EC	0.02	42 b
Carbaryl 50 WP	0.1	42 b
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.07	21 c
No insecticide (control)	Water spray	11 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

Leaf folder (LF) resurgence and species composition in Pattambi, Kerala

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In field trials 1983-85 at Pattambi, LF damage was higher in maximum protection treatments (MPT) (see figure). In both the first crop (May-Aug) and second crop (Sep-Feb), MPT plots receiving carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) recorded higher LF damage (90% in the first crop, 55% in the second) than the no-insecticide plot.

Triazophos effectively controlled LF. Carbosulfan was no different from no insecticide. With synthetic pyrethroid, damage was 10-25%.

To corroborate these findings, we conducted an observational trial in 90-m² plots using EC (emulsifiable

LF damage in Kerala, India, 1983-85.

Control of LF resurgence on variety Annapoorna. Kerala, India, 1983-85.

Insecticide	Application method	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Damaged leaves ^a (%)		
			29 DT ^b	44 DT ^c	60 DT
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	Foliar	0.5	17.9	14.9	2.7
Quinalphos 25 EC	Foliar	0.5	18.3	6.7	0.6
Carbofuran 3 G	Soil	0.75	7.3	56.5	72.5
Quinalphos 5 G	Soil	0.75	10.4	50.6	52.5
Phorate 10 G	Soil	0.75	10.6	34.4	45.2
Monocrotophos 40 EC	Foliar	0.5	14.7	10.3	3.4
No insecticide (untreated control)	-	-	17.7	65.8	70.0

^aComputed from 25 infested hills in each treatment. Insecticides applied 30 and 45 DP. ^b1 d before first application. ^c1 d before second application.

concentrate) and granular insecticide formulations applied at 30 and 45 DT. The results confirmed that, in general, granular insecticide formulations are less effective than EC formulations (see table).

Carbofuran had controlled LF earlier, but resurgence was evident recently. Samples of LF larvae were collected from ricefields and reared in the laboratory. Adults that emerged were identified by wing markings. Adults collected from light traps also were identified.

An estimate for 3 mo Oct to Dec showed that about 50% of the LF population was *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley, which had not been reported in this region before. The rest of the population was common LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. □

Occurrence and infectivity of entomogenous nematodes in mole crickets in Brazil

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In certain regions of the Amazon, mole crickets of the genera *Scapteriscus* and *Neocurtilla* are major pests of rice planted on seasonal floodplains. Although nematodes have been isolated previously from Brazilian mole crickets, work since 1982 on natural enemies has revealed 18 isolates of *Steinernema felitae* (Filipjev) (*Neoaplectana carpocapsae* Weiser) and 13 isolates of *Heterorhabditis* sp. from 1,532 site collections.

Site collections consist of digging mole crickets from each sampled locality and field. Site collections ranged from 1 to more than 500 crickets.

In initial laboratory evaluations, it was impossible to propagate the nematodes on the wax moths *Galleria* sp. usually used for mass production. We screened mole crickets that had been held in the laboratory at least 30 d to ensure they were not infested with nematodes or other pathogenic agents and exposed them to nematodes on